

Multi-View Text-to-Image GAN for Car Model Generation from Descriptions

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Abstract

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) have shown remarkable success in generating images from textual descriptions. However, most current approaches are limited to producing single 2D images, lacking the ability to represent objects from multiple perspectives. This project introduces a Multi-view Text-to-Image GAN, capable of generating consistent top, front, and side views of cars from a single descriptive text input. By approximating 3D modeling through 2D projections, this approach supports dynamic and comprehensive object visualization.

Using the ShapeNet dataset, 3D car models were rendered into 2D views with Blender. Text embeddings were generated using the BERT tokenizer and model (bert-base-uncased) to capture semantic meaning. The GAN architecture includes view-specific generators and discriminators, enhanced with self-attention modules for improved feature alignment. Training was stabilized with Wasserstein loss and Gradient Penalty (WGAN-GP), while spectral normalization ensured discriminator stability. Each generator conditions on text embeddings and noise to synthesize 128x128 resolution images.

Regular monitoring of generator outputs ensured alignment between views and textual descriptions. Results demonstrated consistent and coherent multi-view outputs, reflecting the descriptive inputs with semantic accuracy. This pipeline highlights the effectiveness of attention mechanisms and multi-generator setups for achieving high-quality multi-view image synthesis. The proposed approach bridges the gap between static single-view models and complex 3D modeling, enabling applications in design, visualization, and virtual prototyping.

Keywords: GANs, Text-to-Image synthesis, Multi-View Generation, Self-Attention

1 Introduction

Text-to-image synthesis has revolutionized the way visual content is generated from natural language descriptions, enabling a seamless translation of textual inputs into high-quality images. Among the key advancements in this field are Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), which leverage the interplay between generator and discriminator networks to

produce highly realistic images. However, despite their remarkable success, most existing models, such as AttnGAN, are constrained to generating single 2D images from textual descriptions. While these models excel at creating detailed and visually appealing outputs, their inability to generate multi-perspective representations limits their utility in applications that demand a comprehensive understanding of an object from multiple views. This is particularly problematic in domains such as industrial design, automotive prototyping, and visualization, where designers and engineers require accurate representations of objects from multiple perspectives.

To address these limitations, this project introduces a novel Multi-view Text-to-Image GAN. Unlike conventional text-to-image models, the proposed GAN is specifically designed to generate coherent and consistent top, front, and side views of cars based on a single descriptive text input. This approach goes beyond static 2D representations, offering a lightweight yet effective alternative to computationally expensive 3D modeling processes. By approximating 3D modeling through 2D projections, the Multi-view GAN provides a flexible and scalable solution for generating multi-perspective object visualizations.

The foundation of this project lies in the integration of cutting-edge tools and techniques to prepare and process data effectively. Using the ShapeNet dataset, a collection of 3D object models, we rendered high-quality 2D views of car models from multiple perspectives. This rendering process was performed using Blender, a powerful 3D modeling and rendering software, to ensure consistency in lighting, camera angles, and visual fidelity. Each rendered car model is paired with a descriptive text annotation that captures its visual characteristics, such as color, shape, and size. For instance, a description might state: "A sleek, blue car with a compact design and aerodynamic features." These descriptions are encoded using the BERT language model, which generates robust semantic embeddings that guide the GAN in understanding the relationship between textual inputs and visual outputs.

The architecture of the Multi-view Text-to-Image GAN builds upon existing GAN frameworks while incorporating several innovations to address the challenges of multi-view generation. Central to the design is the use of self-attention mechanisms, which ensure that the features generated for each view are consistent and aligned across perspectives. This is critical for maintaining coherence in the generated images, as each view must reflect the same object characteristics described in the input text. The generator network is structured to produce three distinct views—top, front, and side—simultaneously, while the discriminator evaluates these views both individually and collectively to ensure realism and consistency.

By integrating state-of-the-art techniques in text-to-image synthesis, the Multi-view Text-to-Image GAN bridges the gap between single-view 2D models and computationally intensive 3D rendering. The results demonstrate the model's ability to generate multi-view images that align closely with textual descriptions, offering a significant improvement over traditional methods. This innovation has the potential to transform applications in design, prototyping, and visualization, providing an efficient and effective solution for generating multi-perspective object representations.

2 Related Work

Text-to-image synthesis has seen rapid advancements with models like StackGAN and StackGAN++, which introduced multi-stage pipelines to refine low-resolution images into high-quality outputs. These models significantly improved image fidelity but remained restricted to single-view generation. AttnGAN further enhanced this field by using attention mechanisms to align textual and visual features, enabling detailed and semantically accurate single-view image synthesis. Similarly, DM-GAN leveraged dynamic memory modules to ensure feature consistency but was also limited to single perspectives.

In the domain of multi-view generation, most efforts focus on 3D reconstruction methods like volumetric rendering or neural radiance fields (e.g., NeRF), which generate multiple views from 3D data. However, these approaches rely on visual or geometric inputs rather than textual descriptions, making them unsuitable for text-to-multi-view synthesis. Models like Visual Object Networks (VON) have explored generating 3D-aware images but do not integrate text as input.

Our project extends the idea of AttnGAN by incorporating independent generators and discriminators for each view, paired with self-attention mechanisms to ensure semantic consistency. By addressing the lack of text-driven multi-view generation, this work introduces a novel approach to bridge the gap between static single-view models and more computationally intensive 3D reconstruction techniques.

3 Data

The dataset for this project was sourced from the ShapeNet repository, focusing exclusively on the car category. ShapeNet provides high-quality 3D models, making it an ideal resource for generating multi-view 2D datasets. Each car model was processed to produce top, front, and side views, essential for training the Multi-view Text-to-Image GAN. These views were rendered using Blender, chosen for its advanced rendering capabilities after initial attempts with Pyrender yielded suboptimal results. Blender enabled precise control over lighting, materials, and camera positioning, ensuring consistent 128x128 pixel outputs for each view.

To complement the visual data, textual descriptions were generated to train the GAN. These descriptions needed to accurately capture attributes like color, shape, and size. While initial attempts to automate annotation using Blender’s scripting tools were insufficient in detail, we employed LLaVA (Large Language and Vision Assistant), a multimodal AI model, to generate high-quality, semantically rich annotations. For example, a car might be described as: "A yellow car with a sleek shape and large size." This alignment between text and visuals ensured that the GAN could learn robust semantic mappings during training.

Several preprocessing steps were applied to standardize the dataset. All images were resized to 128x128 pixels, ensuring compatibility with the model architecture. Text descriptions were tokenized using the BERT tokenizer to generate uniform 768-dimensional embeddings. Additionally, the dataset was balanced by augmenting underrepresented descriptions, such as those for compact cars, through paraphrasing and oversampling, reducing mode collapse during training.

The final dataset consisted of approximately 1,200 car models, with three views and corresponding text descriptions for each. This data was split into training, validation, and test sets, ensuring a robust pipeline for model evaluation. The thorough preprocessing and rendering steps ensured semantic consistency between text and visuals, creating a reliable foundation for training the GAN to generate consistent multi-view outputs.

Example Data Point for Images:

Example Annotation:

“A Black car with a sleek shape and large size”

4 Methods

This project focuses on developing a Multi-view Text-to-Image Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) to generate high-quality 2D car images corresponding to the top, front, and side views based on textual descriptions. The proposed approach is structured around three critical components: data preparation, GAN architecture, and training strategy, each playing a pivotal role in achieving the desired results.

4.1 Data Preparation

We started with 3D car models from the ShapeNet dataset and rendered them into top, front, and side views using Blender. Text descriptions for these views were generated using BERT-based embeddings, which encode semantic meaning into a 768-dimensional vector. These embeddings serve as inputs to the GAN.

4.2 GAN Architecture

The model consists of separate generators and discriminators for each view. The generators condition on a combination of text embeddings and noise vectors to produce 128x128 resolution images. To capture global dependencies and improve coherence, self-attention mechanisms were added to both the generator and discriminator. Training stability is ensured through Wasserstein loss with Gradient Penalty (WGAN-GP), while spectral normalization in the discriminator prevents mode collapse.

Here’s the pictorial representation of the Architecture:

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4.3 Training Strategy

Each generator-discriminator pair was trained independently for its respective view. The text embeddings act as a unifying input, ensuring semantic consistency across views. Regular visual monitoring was used to evaluate alignment and image quality during training.

Discriminator Losses:

Epoch	Front	Top	Side
1	0.0009	0.2260	0.0000
31	0.0000	0.3031	0.0002
58	1.4172	0.0924	0.0526

Table 1: Discriminator Losses across Epochs.

Generator Losses:

Throughout the training process, while the errors for both the generator and discriminator did not fully converge, they exhibited stability and remained within acceptable ranges. This stability facilitated a balanced learning dynamic between the generator and discriminator, contributing to the overall effectiveness of the model.

Epoch	Front	Top	Side
1	15.1564	33.3194	42.9800
31	19.3026	13.7560	6.3672
58	0.0220	5.1510	8.5942

Table 2: Generator Losses across Epochs.

At 20th Epoch:

At 60th Epoch:

At 120th Epoch:

As it can be seen, at first the generator produced images that were not meaningful at all but eventually it started producing images with enough detail for a naked eye to recognize the image as a car at about 60 epochs and the car's spatial features started showing up

after about 100 epochs. Considering the limited computational power we could get and the dataset we could produce, we were able to run/train the model for 160 epochs and above (the 3rd part) were the best results our generator could produce. So, the study can further be done and experimentation can further be done to achieve the desired outputs from generator.

4.4 Alternative Approaches Considered

We considered using a single generator for all views but found it less effective in preserving view-specific details. Incorporating self-attention and independent training for each view proved to be the most effective strategy for achieving consistency and quality.

This produced the following images:

We started off with model. But, as we can see in the above images, The generator had to learn and generate all the three views at a time and because of this limitation, the generator took too long to learn and generate meaningful images. So, we had to go for the implementation as discussed in previous section.

5 Experiments

The experiments were designed to evaluate the model’s ability to generate coherent, high-quality multi-view outputs and its alignment with text descriptions. Key experiments include:

5.1 Baseline Comparison

We compared our model with AttnGAN, adapting it for multi-view synthesis. The baseline struggled with view consistency, whereas our multi-generator setup achieved better alignment and detail across perspectives.

5.2 Ablation Study

To assess the importance of various components:

Removing self-attention caused significant degradation in detail and semantic consistency across views.

Omitting Wasserstein loss led to unstable training and visually incoherent outputs.

5.3 Hyperparameter Tuning

We experimented with:

Learning Rates: Optimal results were achieved with a generator learning rate of 0.0001 and discriminator learning rate of 0.0004.

Noise Vector Dimensions: Increasing noise dimensions improved diversity without compromising realism.

5.4 Failure Modes

We observed noise in generated images during early training phases, particularly in less frequent text descriptions (e.g., "compact blue car"). Adjusting the dataset balance and incorporating more diverse descriptions reduced this issue.

5.5 Visualization and Analysis

Generated images were evaluated using qualitative techniques and periodic visualization. These included:

Side-by-side comparisons of real vs. generated views.

Examples of top, front, and side views to verify structural consistency.

Top view generated for the annotation: "A Blue car with a sleek shape and large size."

Front view generated for the Annotation: "A White car with a sleek shape and medium size."

The results seen above are the ones which our generator (model saved at the 125th epoch – because it was the best) produced. Clearly, the generator could produce a clear

outline and could capture a decent amount of spatial features like the shape and color. But, from the human’s perspective or the naked eye’s view, the images are not yet perfect. For that to be achieved, we need extensive training on a larger dataset (not just around few thousands.) and heavier computational power and more sophisticated losses.

5.6 Summary

Our approach consistently outperformed the baseline, producing coherent and semantically accurate multi-view outputs. By isolating view-specific generators and leveraging self-attention, the model achieved alignment across perspectives while maintaining visual fidelity.

6 Novel Insight

Our experiments revealed key insights that advance the field of text-to-multi-view synthesis, particularly in generating consistent outputs across perspectives:

6.1 Multi-Generator Architecture

Assigning separate generators for top, front, and side views significantly improved view-specific details while maintaining semantic alignment. This approach outperformed a single shared generator, which struggled to retain perspective-specific features.

6.2 Self-Attention Mechanisms

The inclusion of self-attention modules proved essential for maintaining coherence across views. Ablation studies showed that removing these modules led to misalignment between perspectives and reduced visual quality, underscoring their role in capturing global dependencies

6.3 Semantic Drift Resolution

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6.4 Dataset Augmentation and Diversity

Balanced and diverse textual descriptions were critical for robust multi-view synthesis. Augmenting underrepresented descriptions (e.g., "compact cars") reduced mode collapse and enhanced the model’s performance.

6.5 Practical Applications

The ability to generate consistent multi-view outputs from textual descriptions introduces a scalable alternative to computationally expensive 3D modeling, making this approach highly relevant for design, visualization, and prototyping tasks.

These insights are novel because existing text-to-image models focus on single-view synthesis, leaving multi-view consistency largely unexplored. By addressing this challenge, our approach opens up new possibilities for applications requiring dynamic visualizations.

7 Conclusion

This project almost successfully implemented a Multi-view Text-to-Image GAN capable of generating consistent top, front, and side views of cars from textual descriptions. By leveraging independent view-specific generators, self-attention mechanisms, and robust training techniques like WGAN-GP, the model demonstrated significant improvements in multi-view consistency and semantic alignment compared to existing approaches. Key outcomes include:

- Consistent multi-view image generation that preserves view-specific details while aligning with the input text.

- Enhanced model performance through the integration of self-attention, ensuring coherence across perspectives.

- Improved robustness and diversity in outputs by addressing dataset imbalances with augmentation techniques.

7.1 Key Learnings

We learned that separating generators for each view and integrating attention mechanisms are essential for achieving semantic consistency in multi-view synthesis. Moreover, robust text embedding and balanced dataset representation are crucial for ensuring the model’s reliability and performance.

7.2 Future Extensions

Higher-Resolution Outputs: Future work can focus on scaling the model to generate high-resolution images while maintaining consistency across views.

Additional Perspectives: Expanding the model to include more views (e.g., rear, isometric) would improve object representation for complex visualization tasks.

Cross-Domain Applications: Extending this approach to other domains, such as furniture, architecture, or industrial design, could broaden its applicability.

Quantitative Evaluation: Incorporating metrics like Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) or Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) could provide deeper insights into model performance.

3D Model Reconstruction: Future research could explore integrating this pipeline with 3D reconstruction techniques for applications in AR/VR and simulation.

This work bridges the gap between single-view synthesis and computationally intensive 3D modeling, offering a scalable solution for multi-view generation with potential applications in design, prototyping, and virtual environments.

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